

Precision And Difference In A Series Of Synonyms

Gafforjon Ruzmatovich Rahmonov

Tashkent University Of Business And Science Llc
Associate professor, philology doctor of philosophy (PhD)

Abstract: In this article, in Uzbek linguistics, in the following years, it is necessary to distinguish the signs of identity and difference in the essence of dictionary synonyms by defining them on the basis of a detailed analysis of their lexical meanings.

Keywords — dictionary synonyms, lexical meaning, semitic analysis, semantic differences, stylistic feature, connotation, subtlety of meaning, emotional colour, dominant, neutral word, semantic event, semasiological basis, semantic structure of the word, sememe, sema, nomeme, precision, difference, generality.

INTRODUCTION

The principle of exactness and difference noted in relation to linguistic units is also observed in lexical synonyms. The linguist O. Bozorov noted that both the content side of the word (lexeme) and the sound side, which is considered to be the material side (form) of change, development, i.e. the characteristic of changes, the emergence of new formations (types of lexemes) on this basis is a natural phenomenon, drawing this process as follows

Content (meaning): exactness → difference → contradiction.

Form (sound shell): exactness → difference → contrast.

If we pay attention, the exactness inherent in the lexemes grows towards the difference - the sign that is the basis of their conflict .

At this point it is necessary to admit that the common meaning, which is characteristic of the members of the paradigm in the synonymous line, i.e. at the same time there are differences which distinguish them from each other and are the basis of the conflict.

Identity is the equality of a thing with itself, it is manifested in the proportion of certain form and content in the size of certain qualitative and quantitative signs, and it prepares the ground for its formation in organic connection with difference.

The exactness observed in the units of the linguistic level can be seen in the correspondence and compatibility of their meaning, form, function, stylistic signs, etc. Such particularities interact with differences and are determined in relation to each other.

While thinking about this, O. Bozorov said that difference is the state of acquisition of relative characteristics of the object as a result of direct strengthening and development of subtle changes within the scope of reality, on the one hand, it is the state of reality, and on the other hand, it is a contradiction (otherness, transformation into other things). Emphasising that it is an intermediate formation related to appearance, shows that linguistic units related to the phenomena of synonymy and polysemy in language can be an example of it .

Therefore, difference is therefore a sign that opens the way to and creates conflict. These two aspects are in a dialectical relationship, since difference arises in the essence of reality. As contradiction grows out of reality as a result of qualitative changes, a new essence emerges in this process. According to E. N. Miller, contradiction is a dialectical negation of exactness, a non-similar appearance of exactness. Contradiction is another specificity, i.e. something new, which is formed by variability, difference (by a gradual “jump”) from exactness, and forms the first link of the subsequent “chain” process (exactness → difference → contradiction) .

It is understood that a chain link is formed in the transition from exactness to difference. In such a chain, exactness is the initial node and difference is the final node. In language, exactly such changes of quality occur in the formation of homonymy.

The principle of mutual differentiation in the relationship of lexemes is particularly evident in antonymic units. An intermediate state is often observed in antonymic lines. For example, the lexeme morning in the antonymic series night→morning→day; and in the antonymic series good→satisfactory→bad, the lexeme satisfactory; in the antonymic series rich→middle→poor, the middle lexeme occupies an intermediate position. In other words, the presence of dawn between night and day, the existence of a satisfactory state between good and bad, or the observation of an intermediate state between rich and poor, shows that these types of antonymic units are not in a double position, but that there is also a third, that is, an intermediate unit in them.

The presence of an intermediate third creates a gradational relationship in antonymic sequences of this type.

In the same way, the presence of an intermediate state between synonyms causes a difference and creates a contradictory relationship. For example, in the synonym line dark → black → darkness, the winter (qorong‘i → zimiston → zim-ziyo) unit occupies an intermediate position. Or bright → shining → light (nurli → yorug‘ → nurafshon), where the lexeme light is in an intermediate position in the synonymous line.

In such a situation there is a levelling of the sign in the meaning of the lexical units. As a result, there is a strong conflict between the initial members of the synonymous line according to the sign level. For example, the strong difference

in the level of the sign of darkness reflected in the lexemes dark and dark means that these lexemes are in conflict according to the level sign. Similarly, in the synonymous line nam → wet → shalabbo, due to the gradation caused by the influence of the lexeme wet, a conflict arises in the relationship between the lexemes nam and shalabbo (wet).

It is clear that the occurrence of intermediate cases not only in lines with antonymic relations, but also in synonymous lines (especially in the line of synonyms, which means quantitative differentiation of a sign) leads to the formation of gradual synonymy in relation to lexemes of this type.

Thus, lexical synonymy represents exactness at the level of language, while gradual synonymy is a linguistic phenomenon that vividly reflects difference at the level of language.

REFERENCES

- [1] Апресян Ю.Д. Лексическая семантика. Синонимические средства языка. – М.: Наука, 1974. – С.368
- [2] Гак В.Г. К проблеме гносеологических аспектов семантики слова. – М., 1971. – С.95;
- [3] Жуманиёзов Р. Синонимлар таърифи масаласи // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. 1970. № 1. – 35 б.
- [4] Нёматов Х., Расулов Р. Ўзбек тили систем лексикологияси асослари. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1995. – 57 б.